

Study of Outcome of Vacuum Assisted Closure in Open Fractures of TibiaShakil Ahmad¹, Ashok Kumar Chaurasia², Shibal Zaheer³, Rakesh Kumar⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar³PGT, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar⁴Associate Professor and HOD, Department of Orthopaedics, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Long bone compound fractures remain a challenge for the treating surgeon despite many advancements. Standard wound dressings had poor patient compliance, required a long time, required repeated debridement, and caused trauma to granulation tissue. Vacuum-assisted closure provides an extremely efficacious method for treating difficult wounds. The purpose of this study was to examine the results of vacuum-assisted closure for open tibia fractures.

Methods: This observational study was conducted at Department of Orthopaedics, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar from March 2024 to August 2024 on patients who were older than eighteen, hemodynamically stable, and had open tibia fractures (G.A. II, IIIA, and IIIB) that had undergone primary internal fixation and vacuum assisted closure (VAC).

Results: The mean age of the 30 patients in this study was 41.34 ± 14.56 years, with the majority (83.33%) being male. From the second day of the post-operative period, VAC dressings were applied every four days; 15 cases (50%) had five VAC dressings applied, 10 cases (33.33%) had four VAC dressings applied, and 5 cases (16.67%) had more than five VAC dressings applied. Mean Hospital stay was 18.82 ± 9.46 days. Post-primary Procedure, majority had Split skin-graft (63.33 %), Repeat debridement and then secondary closure (16.67 %), direct closure (10 %), Tissue transfer (6.67 %) & healing by secondary intension (3.33 %). Mean decrease in wound size was 10.23 ± 3.72 cm². Two cases (6.67%) had implant-related infections, and one case (3.33%) had an exposed implant. At 6 months follow-up, the functional outcome was bad in one case (3.33%), fair in nine cases (30%), good in seventeen cases (56.67%), and excellent in three cases (10%).

Conclusion: Applying VAC lowers the risk of wound infection, speeds up the healing process, and minimizes the need for further soft tissue defect covering procedures.

Keywords: open fractures, fracture tibia, VAC application, NPWT.

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Introduction

High energy open fractures necessitate immediate irrigation and debridement due to their increased risk of infection and soft tissue loss. The most important and clinically significant treatment for these open wounds was thought to be wound healing. Standard wound dressings had low patient compliance, required a long time, required recurrent debridement, and caused additional damage to the granulation tissue.

We have experimented with a variety of techniques over the last fifteen years, such as creating our own antimicrobial cement, using negative pressure to aid in closure, using external fixators, and developing new flap options. We discover that these approaches could be successfully integrated

and cooperate to treat tibia infections connected to implants. In order to improve wound healing, surgical wounds can be drained by applying negative pressure, which generates a suction force. This idea is widely known in the literature. [1–8]

The benefits of both open and closed treatment are combined in VAC therapy's sterile, controlled environment, where wound healing occurs in a clean, moist, and sterile setting. [9–11]

Material and Methods

This observational study was conducted in Department of Orthopedics, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar from March 2024 to August 2024. Total 30 patients aged above 18

years of age, haemodynamically stable with open fractures of tibia {G.A.II, IIIA, and IIIB}, were included in this study. Patients with having pre-existing osteomyelitis in the wounds, neurovascular deficit in the injured limb, having malignancy and anticoagulants, chemotherapy and corticosteroids were excluded in this study.

Patients were informed about the study in their native tongue, and their written agreement was obtained to participate. All patients got main emergency care upon arrival, which included dressings, antibiotics, tetanus toxoids, immobilization, and complete wound cleaning with copious irrigation of normal saline, hydrogen peroxide, and povidone iodine paint. The Gustilo-Anderson classification for open fractures was used to categorize each patient. The dressings were changed on the fourth day after 30 patients with open tibia fractures had undergone primary internal fixation and vacuum assisted closure (VAC) application. Sterile, open-pore foam dressings with pore sizes 400–600 microns were carefully placed onto the wound cavity, and the foam, tubing, and five centimeters of

healthy tissue around it were sealed with an adhesive to ensure a seal. All tissues on the inner surface of the wound were uniformly subjected to controlled pressure, with the pump set to deliver an intermittent negative pressure of 125 mmHg. The cycle was scheduled to last seven minutes, with the pump turning on for five minutes and off for two minutes. The presence of drainage, oedema, erythema, exposed bone or exposed tendon were fairly noted.

All patients were evaluated for an average period of follow up of 12 months. Data was collected and compiled using Microsoft Excel, analysed using SPSS 23.0 version. Statistical analysis was done using descriptive statistics.

Results

The majority of the 30 patients in this study were male (83.33%), had a right side fracture (63.33%), and had a fracture from a traffic accident (80%). The mean age was 41.34 ± 14.56 years, and the majority (40%) and 23.33% were in the 30-39 and 19-29 age groups.

Table 1: General characteristics

Characteristics	No. of patients	Percentage
Age groups (in years)		
19-29	7	23.33%
30-39	12	40%
40-49	5	16.67%
50-59	3	10%
60-69	2	6.67%
70-79	1	3.33%
Mean age (mean±SD) cm ²	41.34 ± 14.56	
Gender		
Male	25	83.33%
Female	5	16.67%
Laterality		
Right	19	63.33%
Left	11	36.67%
Mode of injury		
Road traffic accident (high energy trauma)	24	80%
Fall from height (low energy trauma).	6	20%

G.A. type 3A fractures accounted for 43.33 percent of the majority of cases in this study, followed by G.A. type 2 (30%) and G.A. type 3B (26.67%). From the second day of the post-operative period, VAC dressings were applied every four days; 15

cases (50%) had five VAC dressings applied, 10 cases (33.33%) had four VAC dressings applied, and 5 cases (16.67%) had more than five VAC dressings used. The average length of stay was 18.82 ± 9.46 days.

Table 2: Fracture characteristics

Characteristics	No. of patients	Percentage
Type of fracture (Gustilo-Anderson classification)		
Type2	9	30%
Type 3A	13	43.33%
Type 3B	8	26.67%
Frequency of VAC dressing application		
4	10	33.33%
5	15	50.0%

>5	5	16.67%
Mean Hospital stay (days)	18.82 ± 9.46	

The majority had split skin-graft (63.33%), repeat debridement followed by secondary closure (16.67%), direct closure (10%), tissue transfer (6.67%), and healing by secondary intension (3.33%) after the primary procedure. The mean decrease in wound size was 10.23 ± 3.72 cm².

Implant-related infection was noted in 2 cases (6.67%) and exposed implant in 1 case (3.33%).

At the 1-year follow-up, the functional outcome was excellent in 3 cases (10%), good in 17 cases (56.67%), fair in 9 cases (30%), and poor in 1 case (3.33%).

Table 3: Postoperative characteristics

Characteristics	No. of patients	Percentage
Post-primary Procedure		
Split skin-graft	19	63.33%
Repeat debridement and then secondary closure	5	16.67%
Direct closure	3	10%
Tissue transfer	2	6.67%
Healing by secondary in tension	1	3.33%
Mean decrease in wound size(cm ²)(mean± SD)	10.23 ± 3.72	
Complications		
Implant related infection	2	6.67%
Exposed implant	1	3.33%
Functional outcome (at six months follow up)		
Excellent	3	10%
Good	17	56.6%
Fair	9	30%
Poor	1	3.33%

Discussion

An increased risk of infection, delayed union, non-union, and wound complications is linked to open tibia fractures. In order to promote soft tissue and bone healing, management aims to minimize the risk of infection while maximizing the biological and biomechanical environment. [12] When evaluating and treating compound fractures in the extremities, it is always important to consider a number of factors, such as the patient's condition, the kind of fracture, antimicrobial therapy, wound debridement, the location and extent of the wound, neurovascular state, and the extent of muscle tear. [13,14]

Surgically treating severe open fractures of the lower leg is still very difficult, and treating the underlying soft tissue damage is of utmost importance. Significant soft tissue abnormalities may result from debridement of all non-viable tissue in such accidents. Numerous surgical techniques, such as skin grafts, local rotation flaps, and Myocutaneous or fasciocutaneous tissue transfers, have been devised to achieve covering under these challenging circumstances.

A sophisticated variation of a common surgical procedure, vacuum assisted closure (also known as vacuum therapy, vacuum sealing, or topical negative pressure therapy) uses a vacuum to extract blood or serous fluid from a wound or operation site. By preserving a moist wound environment,

boosting local blood flow, eliminating wound exudates, encouraging granulation tissue, and lowering infection, it facilitates healing. Additional debridement of non-viable tissue can be necessary prior to achieving wound closure or plastic surgical covering. The usage of NPWT exhibits benefits over the conventional wet to dry (WTD) dressings during the intervals between these surgical procedures. NPWT provides protection from nosocomial pollutants and encourages local wound perfusion and drainage by sealing the wound from the hospital environment, serving as a temporary dermal replacement, and preventing bacteria from entering the wound bed. [15]

When vacuum aided closure is applied correctly, the wound bed is nearly completely debrided and adequately irrigated prior to closure, avoiding bacterial access. This can significantly lower the chance of developing a deep infection. [16] Saurabh S. et al. [17] examined 45 patients, 16 of whom were female and 29 of whom were male. There were 15 patients with open left tibia fractures and 25 patients with open right tibia fractures. Seven cases suffered fractures after falling from a height (low energy trauma), while 27 cases suffered fractures after a traffic accident (high energy trauma). Five patients had GA type-2, twenty had GA type 3A, and eight adults had open fractures of both bones in their legs of G.A. type 3B. One benefit of VAC is that it has been shown to speed up the production of granulation tissue on wounds with ex-

posed tendons, bones, raw area wounds, and exposed implants. This reduces the need for further soft tissue defect coverage procedures and speeds up the healing process.

According to the study by Clevio D et al. [18], out of 30 patients treated with modified vacuum assisted dressings, the average total wound size decrease was 15.06 mm, and it took 7.7 days for healthy granulation tissue to develop. When comparing 25 patients who needed a flap as a final closure procedure to 30 patients who received conventional betadine dressings, the mean decrease in wound size was 7.7 mm, and it took 18.8 days for healthy granulation tissue to appear overall.

In contrast, 20 patients had their wounds closed by split skin grafting, and 5 patients had their wounds contracted with treatment. Four patients needed a flap as a final closure procedure, while eight wounds were treated with traditional betadine dressings without the need for a second procedure, and the wounds of eighteen patients were closed by split skin grafting. Both the average duration and the size of the wound have significantly decreased.

In their study of 30 cases, Mittal V et al. [19] assessed each patient clinically following VAC application and after primary fixation for an average follow-up of 12 months. Most patients needed four to five VAC dressings. Wound size decreased by an average of 9.97 cm² [21.22%]. Four of the thirty patients had great results, sixteen had acceptable results, eight had medium results, and two had bad results. In 50 patients treated with VAC, Kartik G [20] found that 12% of them had an infection. Nine days, or 45 (90%) and 12 days, respectively, were needed to produce good granulation tissue and to prepare the wound for skin cover treatments in just five (10%) of the patients.

VAC has the advantage of totally isolating the wound, which lowers the possibility of environmental secondary contamination, and it also lessens limb edema. When edema is reduced, capillary blood flow is enhanced, increasing the amount of oxygen and nutrients that reach the lesion. [21] VAC decreases bacterial colonization of the wound and speeds up the synthesis of collagen and proteins as well as cell division. Its effectiveness in treating chronic wounds has been demonstrated both clinically and financially. [22,23]

Conclusion

This method has produced a superior functional outcome and effectively reduced the size of the wound, infection, and hospital stay. VAC has also been shown to speed up the production of granulation tissue on wounds with exposed tendons, bones, raw area wounds, and exposed implants. This reduces the need for further soft

tissue defect covering treatments and speeds up the healing process.

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